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Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CARE	Collective benefit, Authority control, Responsibility, Ethics principles
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles
IG	Interest Group
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
OS	Open Science
ReSA	Research Software Alliance
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA-KB	RDA Knowledge Base
RSE	Research Software Engineers
TF	Task Force
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology principles
UNESCO	United National Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
WG	Working Group

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1. Introduction

This report is an intermediate update of the work done by Work Package 3 (WP3) of the RDA TIGER project: Landscape Analysis Service, before the final report (D3.5) scheduled in December 2025. This milestone report has a dual objective according to the reader's level of knowledge:

- For newcomers: to serve as an introduction to the WP3 scope and approaches in gathering Open Science (OS) activities and initiatives, including European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and FAIR data-related initiatives,
- For existing collaborators: to provide an update on recent development of the topics covered in earlier reports.

We first introduce the RDA TIGER project's background (section 2), its scope and engagement on OS, followed by a brief description of the WP3's approach (section 3), before reviewing the recent updates (section 4) on the WP3's OS landscape. Section 5 provides a brief aside update of the RDA TIGER WP4 Outputs service, particularly regarding the RDA Knowledge Base progress, before concluding in Section 6.

2. Background

The democratisation of the Internet has propelled access of knowledge and science beyond the traditional institutions, marking a turning point of the Open Science (OS) movement. This movement, which literally means sharing science with everybody and making it accessible to all, has been supported by administrative and global frameworks that define OS, its characteristics and practical recommendations. Box 1 provide examples of OS definitions from the European Union (EU)¹ administration and the UNESCO² intergovernmental organisation.

Box 1. Open Science (OS) definitions within the European Union (EU) and the UNESCO organisation.

Open Science (OS) definitions

OS by European Union: *“an approach to the scientific process that focuses on spreading knowledge as soon as it is available using digital and collaborative technology.”³*

1

research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en (accessed in 2025.05.23)

2 www.unesco.org/en (accessed in 2025.05.23)

3

research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en (accessed in 2025.05.23)

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

OS by UNESCO: “set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefits of scientists and society as a whole”^{4, 5}

In 2015, the EU established a common OS policy, leading to the creation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁶, a seamless environment for sharing and re-using data, across discipline, social and geographic borders. Today, many countries adopt to this OS approach through national initiatives⁷, to the point that OS is now mandatory under Horizon Europe, the EU’s Research and innovation funding programme⁸.

OS doesn’t mean openness without limits; it follows the principle of being “as Open as possible, as closed as necessary”⁹. To guide how to integrate OS practices into project methodologies and workflows, a set of principles has been developed.

Box 2 presents the FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles that apply to digital objects, to ethics and to repositories respectively. FAIR principles are currently required under the Horizon Europe¹⁰ programme.

Box 2. Definition of FAIR, CARE, TRUST principles related to OS approach.

Sets of Principles related to OS

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable): “*emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals*” 2016¹¹

CARE (Collective benefit, Authority control, Responsibility, Ethics): “*guide for data producers, stewards, and publishers to affirm Indigenous rights to self-determination (...) that will ultimately address complex issues related to privacy, future use, and collective interests, and increase the value of data for reuse*” 2020¹²

TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology): “*offer guidance for maintaining the trustworthiness of digital repositories, especially those responsible for the stewardship of research data.*” 2020^{13, 14}

⁴ doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546 (accessed in 2025.05.23)

⁵ doi.org/10.54677/UTCD9302

⁶ digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud (accessed in 2025.05.23)

⁷ conosc.org/os-policies/ (accessed in 2025.05.23)

⁸

research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en (accessed in 2025.05.23)

⁹

rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en#:~:text=What%20does%20E2%80%9Cas%20open%20as,against%20the%20researcher's%20legitimate%20interests. (accessed in 2025.05.23)

¹⁰ rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en (accessed in 2025.05.23)

¹¹ doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (accessed in 2025.05.23)

¹² doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043. (accessed in 2025.05.23)

¹³ www.rd-alliance.org/value_rda/rda-and-trust-principles/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁴ doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7

The Research Data Alliance (RDA)¹⁵ is a collaborative platform that facilitates open data sharing and reuse¹⁶. Its Working Group (WG) activities have demonstrated their effectiveness by delivering widely recognised recommendations within the scientific community, such as the CARE and TRUST principles (see Box 2). To foster alignment and standardisation of RDA WG outputs with OS developments and technologies, the RDA TIGER project¹⁷ was launched in 2023 for a duration of two years. Through a set of services, RDA TIGER leverages the RDA platform to support the creation of standards and recommendations for open sharing, contributing to EOSC partnerships and implementation of FAIR-enabling activities.

3. Landscape Analysis Service

One element of RDA TIGER is the Landscape Analysis Service (WP3). This provides background knowledge of the OS landscape, including EOSC and FAIR data-related activities. The concrete objective of the Landscape Analysis Service is to guarantee that no WG duplicates existing work, and that gaps and emerging challenges in this topic are addressed. To avoid fragmentation OS effort and prevent silos, the Landscape Analysis Service collects information on the overall OS landscape to help the RDA WGs supported by RDA TIGER in fulfilling their mission in alignment with the current OS landscape.

At this time, the Landscape Analysis Service has already published two project deliverables:

- “D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets”¹⁸, published in June 2023, sets out a description of the scope of the service, how the knowledge base has been built and the methodology behind identifying relevant initiatives to include at this early stage of the project.
- “D3.4 Second OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets”¹⁹, published in October 2024, provides an update and extends the ground covered by the earlier D3.1 report.

The Landscape Analysis Service provides an overview of the OS landscape that goes beyond disciplinary and geographic borders. Thus, the service covers initiatives from the following approaches to landscape analysis, as detailed in Figure 1 below:

- Domain agnostic;
- Domain specific;
- Geographic (national and regional).

¹⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁶ doi.org/10.15497/RDA00104 (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁸ [10.5281/zenodo.8096611](https://zenodo.org/record/8096611). (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁹ [10.5281/zenodo.14017309](https://zenodo.org/record/14017309). (accessed 2025.05.27)

Ways of conceptualising the landscape (domain-agnostic):

- RDA Working Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- RDA Task Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- RDA Plenary Pathways (remaining aware that these have historically changed from plenary to plenary);
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)-funded projects (with domain-agnostic focus);
- EOSC Association coordinated Task Forces (with domain-agnostic focus);
- CODATA Task Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- CODATA Working Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- RDA Working Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) initiative Working Groups;
- WorldFAIR Project domain-agnostic activities;
- Global Open Research Commons (GORC) typology of elements;
- Research Software Alliance Task Forces⁴.

Ways of conceptualising the landscape (domain-specific):

- RDA Working Groups (with domain-specific focus);
- CODATA Task Groups (with domain-specific focus);
- CODATA Working Groups (with domain-specific focus);
- Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) initiative Case Studies;
- WorldFAIR Project Case Studies;
- EOSC-funded projects (with domain-specific focus).

Ways of conceptualising the landscape (national approaches)

- RDA National groups: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-groups>;
- CODATA National Committees: <https://codata.org/membership/national-members/>;
- Research Software Engineers national/multinational associations;
- Potentially the EOSC Observatory (currently under development): <https://eosc-portal.eu/news-and-events/news/introducing-eosc-observatory>.

Figure 1. Research approaches used to scrutinise OS activities for the Landscape Analysis Service, taken from D3.1.

As mentioned in section 1, above, this document provides a brief update of the previous D3.4 report. It offers a snapshot of the OS landscape by community and outlines emerging trends. The descriptions of the communities covered in the earlier reports will not be detailed here, and readers are invited to refer to those earlier deliverables for more information. Only new initiatives or projects will be described.

4. Overview of updates

4.1. Domain agnostic initiatives

4.1.1. RDA community

4.1.1.1. RDA domain-agnostic groups

Table 1 shows the current number of domain agnostic RDA WGs and IGs, at the time of writing (May 2025).

	Number of RDA WGs	Number of RDA IGs
Domain agnostic	21 ²⁰	29 ²¹
Total	44 ²²	48 ²³

Table 1. Numbers of domain agnostic RDA WGs and IGs.

Since the previous D3.4 report published in October 2024, one new IG, ‘Complex Citation Implementation Interest Group’ (CCI IG)²⁴ has been created, along with the development of four new WGs:

- Data Stewards Career Tracks WG²⁵,
- Common Application programming Interface (API) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) WG²⁶ (supported by RDA TIGER),
- Sample Type Classification WG²⁷,
- RDA Reproducibility Checklist WG²⁸ (supported by RDA TIGER).

²⁰www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=domain-agnostic (accessed 2025.05.16)

²¹www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group&_primary_domain=domain-agnostic (accessed 2025.05.16)

²²www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences (accessed 2025.05.17)

²³www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic (accessed 2025.05.17)

²⁴<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citation-implementation-interest-group-cci-ig/activity/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

²⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-steward-career-tracks-wg/activity (accessed 2025.05.27)

²⁶

www.rd-alliance.org/groups/common-application-programming-interface-api-for-machine-actionable-data-management-plans-madmps/activity (accessed 2025.05.17)

²⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/sample-type-classification-wg/activity (accessed 2025.05.17)

²⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-reproducibility-checklist-working-group/activity (accessed 2025.05.17)

4.1.1.2. RDA domain-agnostic outputs

Since the publication of the D3.4 report in October 2024, 3 out of 5 outputs are related to the domain-agnostic domain have been released²⁹:

- RDA & External Reproducibility Efforts³⁰, by the Reproducibility IG³¹ ;
- Precise, Actionable Reference To Dynamic Data: Recommendations Of The Working Group On Data Citation (WGDC) Version: 2025-04-04T08:30Z³², by the Data Citation WG³³
- Complex Citation Working Group Recommendation³⁴, by the Complex Citation WG³⁵

Two outputs from the RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS) WG³⁶ have been published under the “Working Groups Other Outputs” category³⁷. These are: Identifying Gaps in Research Software Policy³⁸ and Resources for supporting policy change in research institutions in practice³⁹

4.1.1.3. RDA Plenary Pathways

The virtual RDA's 24th Plenary meeting⁴⁰ took place from 7-11 April 2025, under the theme “Data for emerging technologies”. For this 24th Plenary, nine pathways⁴¹ were selected to represent the high-level topics of the RDA ecosystem, including a newly introduced pathway: “AI meets data: exploring use cases, applications and innovation” (Table 2). This addition reflects the RDA community interest in AI and its recognition of the importance of addressing challenges related to data quality and legal issues⁴². Table 2 shows the evolution of RDA Pathways as analysed by Landscape Analysis Service in reports D3.1 (2023), and D3.4 (2024). For more details on the RDA P24, the report is now available online⁴³.

Table 2. Overview of RDA Pathways presented at the RDA Plenary.

Year	2023	2024	2025
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²⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?start_date=2024-10-01%2C&end_date=%2C2025-05-29 (accessed 2025.05.04)

³⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/reproducibility-ig/outputs/?output=187176 (accessed 2025.06.04)

³¹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/reproducibility-ig/activity/ (accessed 2025.06.04)

³² www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-citation-wg/outputs/?output=187079 (accessed 2025.06.04)

³³ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-citation-wg/activity/ (accessed 2025.06.04)

³⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group/outputs/?output=173981 (accessed 2025.06.04)

³⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group/activity/ (accessed 2025.06.04)

³⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-resa-policies-research-organisations-research-software-pro4rs/activity/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

³⁷ https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_output_type=working-group-other-output (accessed 2025.06.30)

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15411757> (accessed 2025.06.30)

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11529659> (accessed 2025.06.30)

⁴⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/rda-p24-programme-overview/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁴¹ www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-24th-plenary-pathways/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁴² www.rd-alliance.org/value_rda/rda-and-artificial-intelligence/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁴³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/report-on-the-24th-rda-plenary-vp24-released/> (accessed 2025.06.10)

RDA Plenary	P22 ⁴⁴	P23 ⁴⁵	P24 ⁴⁶
Number of Pathways	8	10	9
Names of the Pathways	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Principles	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Adoption	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Adoption and Implementation
	Data Infrastructures and Environments	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Implementation	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Evaluation and Policy
	Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Evaluation and Policy	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Generalist
	Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Generalist	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Discipline Focused
	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Discipline Aligned	Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning
	Discipline Focused Data Issues	Training, Stewardship skill, and Data Management Planning	Semantics, Ontology, and Standardisation
	Research Software	Semantics, Ontology, and Standardization	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward
	Other	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, Reward, and Preservation	AI meets data: exploring use cases, applications and innovation
		Discipline-Focused Sessions	Other
Other			

4.1.2. EOSC ecosystem

4.1.2.1. EOSC Horizon Europe-funded projects

There are currently 33 ongoing projects in the current EOSC ecosystem⁴⁷. Table 3 lists the Horizon Europe-funded projects under the INFRA-EOSC programme, organised by call year, and shows the growing number of funded-projects over time. Following the 2024 call, ten new projects have been launched and have already started.

Table 3. INFRA-EOSC funded-projects by year of the call. Projects are coloured according to their domain field: Natural Science in blue, Engineering and Technology in green, Interdisciplinary in violet, and Agnostic in orange.

⁴⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-22nd-plenary-pathways-programme-navigation/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁴⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-23rd-plenary-pathways/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁴⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-24th-plenary-pathways/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁴⁷ eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/#openproject (accessed 2025.05.16)

Year of the call	2022	2023	2024
Number of funded-projects	5 ⁴⁸	9 ⁴⁹	10 ^{50;51}
Name of the funded-projects	GraspOS ⁵²	EVERSE ⁵³	DataGEMS ⁵⁴
	CRAFT-OA ⁵⁵	OSTrails ⁵⁶	EOSC Data Commons ⁵⁷
	Blue-Cloud 2026	SIESTA ⁵⁸	EOSC EDEN ⁵⁹
	AquaINFRA ⁶⁰	EOSC Track ⁶¹	CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC ⁶²
	RDA TIGER ⁶³	EOSC Beyond ⁶⁴	EOSC Gravity ⁶⁵
		TITAN ⁶⁶	FIDELIS ⁶⁷
		OSCARS ⁶⁸	LUMEN ⁶⁹
		EOSC-ENTRUST ⁷⁰	RAISE Suite ⁷¹
		HORIZON-ZEN ⁷²	FAIR2Adapt ⁷³
		*EOSC United ⁷⁴	

⁴⁸cordis.europa.eu/search?q=contenttype%3D%27project%27%20AND%20%2Fproject%2Frelations%2Fassociations%2FrelatedMasterCall%2Fcall%2Fidentifier%3D%27HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC%27&p=1&num=10&srt=Relevance:decreasing (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁴⁹cordis.europa.eu/search?q=contenttype%3D%27project%27%20AND%20%2Fproject%2Frelations%2Fassociations%2FrelatedMasterCall%2Fcall%2Fidentifier%3D%27HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC%27&p=1&num=10&srt=Relevance:decreasing (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁵⁰cordis.europa.eu/search?q=contenttype%3D%27project%27%20AND%20%2Fproject%2Frelations%2Fassociations%2FrelatedMasterCall%2Fcall%2Fidentifier%3D%27HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC%27&p=1&num=10&srt=Relevance:decreasing (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁵¹eosc.eu/news/nine-new-horizon-europe-infraeosc-projects-to-launch-in-2025/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵²www.craft-oa.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵³everse.software/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵⁴cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188416 (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵⁵www.craft-oa.eu/

⁵⁶ostrails.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵⁷www.eosc-data-commons.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵⁸eosc-siesta.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁵⁹eden-fidelis.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁰aquainfra.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶¹www.openaire.eu/eosc-track-project (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶²climate-adapt4eosc.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶³www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/ accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁴www.eosc-beyond.eu/about (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁵eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/eosc-gravity/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁶titan-eosc.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁷eden-fidelis.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁸oscars-project.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁶⁹lumenproject.eu/lumen-project-launched-in-january-2025/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷⁰eosc-entrust.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷¹cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188337 (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷²about.zenodo.org/projects/horizon-zen/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷³ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/projects-details/43108390/101188256/HORIZON?isExactMatch=true&order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=es_SortDate (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷⁴ From Call “Future Engagement Model for the EOSC Federation” (INFRA-2024-EOSC-02) ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/projects-results?isExactMatch=true&topicAbbreviation=HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-02-01&order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=es_SortDate (accessed 2025.05.27)

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In May 2025, the 2025 INFRA-EOSC call for proposal⁷⁵ was opened, featuring five topics⁷⁶ aimed to consolidating the EOSC ecosystem:

- EOSC Nodes with federating capabilities for the EOSC Federation
- FAIR Integration for Enhanced Research Data in the EOSC ecosystem and beyond
- Advancing AI-readiness and Machine-Actionability in the EOSC Ecosystem
- Data stewards, skills and training for Open Science and FAIR practices
- Using Generative AI (GenAI4EU) for Scientific Research via EOSC.

4.1.2.2. EOSC Association

Since the beginning of 2025, eleven outputs⁷⁷ have been published to the Macro-Roadmap⁷⁸, the interactive catalogue tracking the results of EOSC projects and EOSC Task Forces (TFs)⁷⁹. In addition, the EOSC Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) WG⁸⁰, part of the ‘Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force’, one of the five EOSC TFs, has recently published recommendations for the initial implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation⁸¹. The publication is available on the Zenodo repository of the EOSC Association (ESOC-A)⁸².

Since the D3.4 report, a new group - EOSC OA Research Software⁸³ - has been added to the list of EOSC Opportunity Area (OA) Expert groups⁸⁴, bringing the total to seven groups. Meanwhile, the EOSC OA, ‘Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability’ group is currently developing approaches to shared interoperability solutions.

4.1.2.3. EOSC Federation

In March 2025, a major milestone was reached with the release of the 1st edition of the EOSC Federation Handbook⁸⁵, which offers practical guidance on key components of the EOSC Federation such as architecture, governance, operations, and policies. Additionally, it's important to mention that in June 2025, the EOSC Gravity⁸⁶ project will succeed the

⁷⁵

rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-research-infrastructures/enabling-operational-op-en-and-fair-eosc-ecosystem-infraeosc_en (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷⁶

assets.ctfassets.net/cdx728z92xkc/JeVTIDFJoXIUFHQPIZo1/031e609a137fc76b3373f991f63608ef/ec_rtd_ri-info-day-2025-agenda.pdf (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷⁷ eosc.eu/eosc-about/eosc-macro-roadmap/?_reporting_year=2025&_type_of_result_mrm=report (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷⁸ eosc.eu/eosc-about/eosc-macro-roadmap/?_type_of_result_mrm=report (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁷⁹ eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸⁰ eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-and-semantic-interoperability-task-force/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸¹ zenodo.org/records/15388270 (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸² zenodo.org/communities/eosc/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸³ eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa7-research-software/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸⁴ eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸⁵ eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸⁶ eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/eosc-gravity/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

EOSC Focus project ⁸⁷ to support the EOSC Federation by encouraging the creation of EOSC Nodes, inter-project collaboration, and support of the revision of SRIA 2.0⁸⁸.

4.1.3. Research Software Alliance

Since the D3.4 report, two new Task Forces (TFs) have joined the Research Software Alliance (ReSA) TFs⁸⁹: ‘Actionable FAIR4RS’⁹⁰, which aims to make research software FAIR, and ‘FAIR Principles for Research Software’ (FAIR4RS), which promotes FAIR principles for research software and is currently under review before adoption.

4.2. Domain specific initiatives

4.2.1. RDA community

4.2.1.1. RDA domain specific groups

Table 4 shows the current number of RDA WGs and IGs by domain of discipline, at the time of writing.

Table 4. Numbers of RDA WGs and IGs by domain

	Number of RDA WGs	Number of RDA IGs
Domain specific	23 ⁹¹	19 ⁹²
Domain agnostic	21 ⁹³	29 ⁹⁴
Total	44 ⁹⁵	48 ⁹⁶

⁸⁷ eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁸⁸ eosc.eu/eosc-about/sria-mar/ (accessed 2025.06.01)

⁸⁹ www.researchsoft.org/taskforces/ (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁹⁰ www.researchsoft.org/tf-actionable-fair4rs/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁹¹ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=working-group&primary_domain=natural-sciences%2CEngineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁹² www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=interest-group&primary_domain=natural-sciences%2CEngineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁹³ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=working-group&primary_domain=domain-agnostic (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁹⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=interest-group&primary_domain=domain-agnostic (accessed 2025.05.16)

⁹⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=working-group&primary_domain=natural-sciences%2CEngineering-and-technology%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences (accessed 2025.05.17)

⁹⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=interest-group&primary_domain=natural-sciences%2CEngineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic (accessed 2025.05.17)

While there are a total of 66 WGs⁹⁷ and 70 IGs⁹⁸, the remaining groups fall into categories outside of the domains of activity, such as regional or coordinating groups (see section 4.3.1, below).

4.2.1.2. RDA domain-specific outputs

Since the publication of the D3.4 report in October 2024, two WG outputs⁹⁹ have been released from two different domain field:

- Social Science: Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal Foundations¹⁰⁰, by Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG¹⁰¹
- Natural Science: MOMSI WG Multi-Omics Standard Landscape Review Curation Workflow & Interactive Web-Based Dashboard Tool¹⁰², by Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG¹⁰³.

4.2.2. EOSC ecosystem

4.2.2.1. EOSC Horizon Europe-funded projects

The newly funded INFRA-EOSC project, ‘Open Science Clusters’ Action for Research and Society’ (OSCARS)¹⁰⁴, works on consolidating past achievements of five thematically oriented research infrastructures (RI), the Science Clusters¹⁰⁵. Through two OSCARS Open Calls, the project aims to engage a broad range of communities in the OS by promoting the adoption of FAIR data services and working practices through inter-cluster cross-adoption and collaborative service development. The 1st OSCARS Open Call funded 58 projects¹⁰⁶ (Table 5), which have started over the past six months. The 2nd OSCARS Open Call¹⁰⁷ closed in May 2025.

Table 5. Number of the OSCARS funded projects from the 1st OSCARS Open Call by domain of discipline and Science cluster

⁹⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁹⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group (accessed 2025.05.27)

⁹⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_start_date=2024-10-01%2C&_end_date=%2C2025-05-29 (accessed 2025.06.04)

¹⁰⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/outputs/?output=175108 (accessed 2025.06.04)

¹⁰¹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/activity/ (accessed 2025.06.04)

¹⁰² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/multi-omics-metadata-standards-integration-momsi-wg/outputs/?output=188206> (accessed 2025.06.04)

¹⁰³ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/multi-omics-metadata-standards-integration-momsi-wg/activity/ (accessed 2025.06.04)

¹⁰⁴ oscars-project.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁰⁵ science-clusters.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁰⁶ oscars-project.eu/news/browse-open-science-projects-and-services-funded-1st-oscars-open-call (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁰⁷ oscars-project.eu/news/opening-announcement-2nd-oscars-open-call-open-science-projects-and-services (accessed 2025.05.27)

Domain	Earth and Environmental Sciences	Astronomy and Particle Physics	Life Sciences	Photon and Neutron Science	Social Sciences and Humanities	Across or outside the domains covered by the clusters
Name of the cluster	ENVRI Science ¹⁰⁸	ESCAPE ¹⁰⁹	LS RI ¹¹⁰	PaNOSC ¹¹¹	SSHOC ¹¹²	-
Number of project funded	7	9	8	6	10	18

The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹¹³ output of the WorldFAIR project¹¹⁴, completed in 2024, is now being implemented in the Photon and Neutron Science cluster through the ‘Describing X-Ray Spectroscopy Data for Cross-Domain Use’ (CDIF-4-XAS) project¹¹⁵ funded by the 1st OSCARS Open Call. CDIF-4-XAS published its first result deliverable in February 2024 and is available on Zenodo¹¹⁶. The next output will provide mappings of two XAS standards (XDI and NXxas) to CDIF, assisting interoperability and reuse. The project will then demonstrate how this can be implemented in Galaxy workflows.

CDIF is also being implemented, refined and extended in the Climate-Adapt4EOSC project, and some other European and international projects outside EOSC. CODATA is maintaining the CDIF Working Group and subgroups to coordinate these activities.

4.2.2.2. EOSC Federation

¹⁰⁸ envri.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁰⁹ projectescape.eu/about-us (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹⁰ lifescience-ri.eu/home.html (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹¹ www.panosc.eu/about-panosc/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹² www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-ssh-open-cluster (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹³ The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework is now presented as the CDIF Book:

<https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

¹¹⁴ worldfair-project.eu/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹⁵ oscars-project.eu/projects/cdif-4-xas-describing-x-ray-spectroscopy-data-cross-domain-use (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹⁶ doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14920226 (accessed 2025.05.27)

Figure 2. Overview of the 13 organisations invited at the kick-off workshop of EOSC federation to represent national and thematic Nodes, taken from EOSC-A news webpage¹¹⁷

A group of 13 organisations¹¹⁸ (Fig.2) has been invited to the EOSC EU Node kick-off workshop to represent thematic and national nodes connecting to the federation (see section 4.1.2.3 for more details about EOSC Federation). EOSC Beyond¹¹⁹ is testing integration with its pre-production EOSC environment through a series of regional and thematic EOSC Pilot Nodes¹²⁰, connecting national, regional, and thematic infrastructures. The Horizon Europe 2025 call “HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-01”¹²¹ aims to develop and expand the EOSC Federation through a network of EOSC Nodes with federating capabilities to strengthen the EOSC Federation.

4.3. Geographic: National and regional

4.3.1. RDA community

RDA recognises the importance of engaging national and regional members into its activities.

Figure 3. RDA Regional Engagement, taken from RDA Regional Membership webpage¹²²

¹¹⁷ eosc.eu/news/eoscs-build-up-phase-to-begin-with-march-kick-off/ (accessed 2025.06.02)

¹¹⁸ eosc.eu/news/eoscs-build-up-phase-to-begin-with-march-kick-off/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹¹⁹ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹²⁰ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilots> (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹²¹ <https://www.horizon-europe.gouv.fr/eosc-nodes-federating-capabilities-eosc-federation-40212> (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹²² www.rd-alliance.org/membership/regional-membership/ (accessed 2025.06.03)

Figure 3 shows the 2025 update of RDA Regional engagement¹²³ by engagement categories. 8 are considered as partners of RDA foundation with a financial contribution, 5 are considered as committed regions with MoU agreement but without financial contribution, 18 are considered as engaged regions with only national or regional webspace within RDA and 4 are considered as interested, indicating an interest to join the RDA community. Moreover, RDA TIGER is also working on preparing a report titled D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs, which aims to concretely describe how RDA TIGER activities are being implemented within the European community and European National Networks. The D2.3 report will be available at the end of June 2025.

There are currently 34 regional groups¹²⁴ and 9 global groups¹²⁵, within the RDA community, compared to the 30 regional groups reported in report D3.4. Regional groups are divided across five locations: Australasia, Asia, America, Southern Europe. Table 6 shows the number of RDA groups available by region.

Table 6. Number of RDA groups by regions.

	Europe ¹²⁶	South America ¹²⁷	Australia ¹²⁸	North America ¹²⁹	Asia ¹³⁰
Number of RDA groups	26	3	2	2	1

Regarding the RDA Coordination Group for the Regions, there are currently 95 members¹³¹, with twelve new members in the last seven months.

4.3.2. EOSC ecosystem

In collaboration with EOSC Focus project¹³², the EOSC-A Country page^{133,134} was developed to provide a detailed overview of national developments in key OS components such as policies, institutional frameworks, and key stakeholders. Since the D3.4 report, Portugal and Ireland have released new OS policies.

¹²³ www.rd-alliance.org/membership/regional-membership/ (accessed 2025.06.03)

¹²⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=regional-group (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹²⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=global (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹²⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=europe (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹²⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=south-america (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹²⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=australia (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹²⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=north-america (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹³⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=asia (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹³¹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-regions/members/all-members/ (accessed 2025.05.17)

¹³² eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-focus-project/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹³³ eosc.eu/news/stay-up-to-date-on-open-science-developments-with-eosc-a-country-pages/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹³⁴ eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/#countries (accessed 2025.05.27)

4.3.3. CODATA

There are currently eighteen CODATA national committees¹³⁵, including Austria, Australia, Botswana, Canada, China, Finland, India, Israel, Japan, Kenya, Korea, Mongolia, New Zealand, South Africa, Taiwan (Taipei), Ukraine, United Kingdom, and the United States of America. Canada and Russia have withdrawn, while Chile has joined as a new committee.

4.3.4. Research Software Engineers

There are currently 9 Research Software Engineers (RSE) national/multinational association¹³⁶ groups: Belgium, Germany, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand, United States, Denmark, Asia and France. Asia and France have recently joined the RSE community, while the Australia and New Zealand groups have merged into a single entity. The Swiss RSE group is currently under development.

4.3.5. National, regional initiatives and networks

It has a panel of various initiatives or networks focusing not only on OS activities related to data sharing or e-infrastructure but also on closely related areas such as education and scholarly collaboration. It is important to follow and keep an eye on the many diverse global networks, as some of these activities are closely connected to data-sharing challenges and may have corresponding outputs.

4.3.5.1. Research and Education Networks

National Research and Education Networks (NRENs)¹³⁷ is one of these initiatives as it contributes “*on behalf of the higher education community to provide advanced information technology and communications services for connecting academic institutions to each other’s networks, and to each other’s resources, both nationally and globally.*”¹³⁸ The Géant Association Compendium of National Research and Education Networks in Europe published in 2014 a list of all the Géant partner NRENs¹³⁹, covering more than 100 countries all over the world. Follow, few examples of Géant partner NRENs based on the region area:

¹³⁵ codata.org/membership/national-members/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹³⁶ researchsoftware.org/assoc.html (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹³⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_research_and_education_network

¹³⁸ *The Role and Status of National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) in Africa*. 2017. World Bank Education

<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/233231488314835003> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹³⁹

<https://web.archive.org/web/20150919142441/http://www.terena.org/publications/files/Compendium-2014.pdf> (accessed 2025.06.27)

- Europe: Réseau national de télécommunications pour la technologie, l'enseignement et la recherche (Renater)¹⁴⁰, Nordic Gateway for Research and Education (NORDUnet)¹⁴¹, German National Research and Education Network (DFN)¹⁴² ;
- Africa: Western and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)¹⁴³, Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)¹⁴⁴, Ubuntunet Alliance (UA)¹⁴⁵;
- Latin America: RedCLARA¹⁴⁶, which include a cooperation of NRENs across seven latin american countries;
- Asia: Trans-Eurasia Information Network (TEIN)¹⁴⁷, CAREN Co-operation Centre (CAREN CC)¹⁴⁸ ;
- Pacific: Australia's national research and education network (AARNET)¹⁴⁹, Research Education Advanced Network New Zealand (REANNZ)¹⁵⁰ ;
- North America: Canada's National Research and Education Network (CANARIE)¹⁵¹, Internet2¹⁵², Energy Sciences Network (ESnet)¹⁵³.

NRENs can also collaborate with one another, creating a broader hub of regional initiatives such as

- AfricaConnect3¹⁵⁴ project which supports National (NRENs) (WACREN, ASREN, UA) and Regional Research and Education Networks (RRENs) in Africa.
- African Research and Education Network (AFREN)¹⁵⁵, organised by Association of African Universities (AAU)¹⁵⁶, is a forum aimed at building an inclusive African research and education network community, bringing together a network of more than 30 research and education networks across African countries.

Global initiatives on research and education are also developed, such as

- Advanced North Atlantic (ANA)¹⁵⁷ brings together the efforts of North American (CANARIE, Internet2, ESnet) and European NRENs (GEANT, NORDUnet, SURFnet);

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.renater.fr/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴¹ <https://nordu.net/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴² <https://www.dfn.de/en/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴³ <https://wacren.net/en/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.asren.net/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴⁵ <https://ubuntunet.net/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.redclara.net/en/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.tein3.net/Pages/home.html> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.caren.geant.org/Pages/Welcome%20to%20the%20CAREN%20website.html> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁴⁹ <https://aarnet.edu.au/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.reannz.co.nz/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵¹ <https://www.canarie.ca/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵² <https://internet2.edu/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵³ <https://www.es.net/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵⁴ <https://africaconnect3.net/project/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵⁵ <https://aau.org/current-projects/afren/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵⁶ <https://aau.org/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵⁷

<https://internet2.edu/network/initiatives-partnerships/global-networks-and-partnerships/advanced-north-atlantic-ana/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

- Global Research and Education Network (GREN)¹⁵⁸, is a network of network of RENS which “*integrate extensive collaboration and coordination between the NRENs across the world and their regional networks*”¹⁵⁹;
- Global Network Advancement Group (GNA-G)¹⁶⁰ is a worldwide collaboration to support the global REN community.

4.3.5.2. Data science training

Contributing to data literacy culture through education and scholarship is also an approach to strengthening adequate skills and supporting the sharing of research assessment practices. These initiatives can be regional, such as those supported by Horizon Europe programme, thought the creation of competence centers, like the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Networks¹⁶¹, European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence (EVERSE)¹⁶², CLuster Open Science Competence Centre (CLOCC)¹⁶³ supported by OSCARS¹⁶⁴, and EuroScienceGateway¹⁶⁵ supported by GALAXY¹⁶⁶.

Other initiatives are global such as the Carpentries¹⁶⁷, International Open Science & Open Scholarship communities (OSC)¹⁶⁸, a community network involved in 27 countries over the world, or specific groups within RDA alliance, such as the Data Stewards Career Tracks WG¹⁶⁹ or the Professionalising Data Stewardship (PDS) IG¹⁷⁰. RDA PGS IG also collaborates with various national initiatives such as:

- Irish Data Stewardship Network Sonrai¹⁷¹;
- Dutch Data Stewards Interests Group¹⁷²;
- Italian Data Steward Community, via the Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (CIDS)¹⁷³;
- Austria has a National Strategy and Alignment for Data Stewardship¹⁷⁴;
- Open Science Competence Network – Data Steward Poland¹⁷⁵;

¹⁵⁸ <https://www.canarie.ca/nren/gren/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁵⁹ <https://nordu.net/gren-2/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶⁰ <https://www.gna-g.net/about-us/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶¹ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶² <https://everse.software/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶³ <https://oscars-project.eu/news/clusters-open-science-competence-centres-definition-and-next-steps> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶⁴ <https://oscars-project.eu/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶⁵ <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶⁶ <https://galaxyproject.org/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹⁶⁷ <https://carpentries.org/about-us/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶⁸ <https://osc-international.com/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁶⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-steward-career-tracks-wg/activity/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/professionalising-data-stewardship-ig/activity/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁷¹ <https://datastewards.ie/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁷² <https://www.dtls.nl/about/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁷³ <https://www.icdi.it/en/news-en/230-italian-data-steward-community-meeting-on-challenges-and-obstacles-in-the-path-towards-a-research-data-policy> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁷⁴ <https://doi.org/10.21240/zfhe/SH-F/05> (accessed 2025.06.27)

¹⁷⁵ <https://eosc.gov.pl/en/usecase/open-science-competence-network-data-steward-pl/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

- Latvia Data Stewards^{176, 177}
- Portuguese Data Stewards Network¹⁷⁸
- Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC), FAIR data stewards course¹⁷⁹

4.3.5.3. Other initiatives and networks

Other initiatives and networks are outlined in Table 7, which presents a non-exhaustive overview of these efforts.

Table 7. List of initiatives and networks closely linked to OS activities (non-exhaustive list).

Region	Name (Abbreviation)	URL (accessed 2025.05.17)
Africa	Digital Hub for Open Research in East Africa	www.templetonworldcharity.org/projects-resources/project-database/33195
Africa	Data Science Without Borders (DSWB)	dswb.africa/
Africa	African Population and Health Research Center (APHRC)	https://aphrc.org/
Africa	Africa Open Science Platform (AOSP)	aosp.org.za/
Africa	South African Open Science Cloud (SAOSC)	www.egi.eu/project/sa-eu-dialogue-saosc/
Africa	Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa (DIRISA)	www.dirisa.ac.za/
Africa	Regional Universities Forum for Capacity Building in Agriculture (RUFORUM)	www.ruforum.org/
Africa	Human Heredity and Health in Africa (H3Africa)	www.h3abionet.org/ (completed)
Africa	eLwazi Open Data Science Platform (eLwazi)	https://elwazi.org/
Africa	Data Science for Health Discovery and Innovation in Africa (DS-I Africa)	https://dsi-africa.org/#about
Asia	Asia Pacific Advanced Network (APAN)	https://apan.net/
Africa	AfriGEOSS	cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020-SFS-43-2017 (completed)
Africa	GODAN Africa	https://aims.fao.org/in-action/events/catalyzing-east-africas-land-data-ecosystem
Africa	Implementation Network for Sharing Population Information from Research Entities (INSPIRE)	https://inspiredata.africa/
Africa	Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	www.gbif.org/the-gbif-network/africa
Africa	South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR)	sadilar.org/en/
Africa	Africa Information Highway	www.afdb.org/en/knowledge/statistics/africa-information-highway-aih
Africa	Communauté d'Afrique Francophone des Données Ouvertes (CAFDO)	https://www.cafdo.africa/

¹⁷⁶ <https://vpc.lv/data-stewards/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹⁷⁷ https://www.izm.gov.lv/en/article/latvian-open-science-strategy-2021-2027-now-english?utm_source=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹⁷⁸ <https://www.fct.pt/en/re-data-lanca-novo-inquerito-nacional-sobre-profissionais-de-apoio-a-gestao-de-dados-de-investigacao/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

¹⁷⁹ <https://neic.no/fairdatastewardscourse/> (accessed 2025.06.30)

America	La Referencia	www.lareferencia.info/en/nodes
America	Data Observatory - Chile	https://dataobservatory.net/
America	RDA-US	rda-us.org/
America	Digital Research Alliance of Canada	www.alliancecan.ca/en
Asia	eResearch South East Asia	www.ersea.org/
Asia	Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)	asean.org/
Australasia	Australasian eResearch Organisations (Aero)	aero.edu.au/
Australasia	Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)	ardc.edu.au/
Australasia	Australian Scalable Drone Cloud (ASDC)	asdc.io/
Europe	NFDI	www.nfdi.de/?lang=en
Europe	European Strategy Forum on Research and Innovation (ESFRI)	https://www.esfri.eu/
Europe	European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

5. Contribution of the RDA Knowledge Base

Since D3.4, the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB)¹⁸⁰, developed by the RDA TIGER WP4 Outputs Service, has made significant progress. Three consecutive workshops were held for RDA members in May 2025 to promote the RDA-KB and gather feedback. The first workshop¹⁸¹ was a beta launch of the RDA-KB, introducing an early version of its suite of services, while the second and third¹⁸² workshops provided a more in-depth demonstration of features, hands-on testing, and opportunities to provide feedback and questions. Guidance documents are now available on the website to assist users, and a feedback service has been implemented to collect user questions. The beta version of the RDA-KB is already available for use by RDA-Users.

Particularly relevant for landscape analysis purposes is the RDA Discovery tool, which provides tools that allows users to easily search the entire RDA corpus using multiple search filters. This tool has recently been updated to provide better search functionality and user experience.

The RDA Annotator¹⁸³ is a service of the RDA-KB that allows RDA users to annotate text-snippets from any web-based resources with descriptions and RDA-related metadata, which are then passed to the RDA-KB for other users to access. This allows RDA users to capture useful information at a very granular level which may not make it into published reports, allowing other users to find and contextualise such information in the future. This functionality makes it particularly useful for landscape analysis efforts. An early version of

¹⁸⁰ rda.dansdemo.nl/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁸¹ www.rd-alliance.org/event/rda-tiger-knowledge-base-beta-launch/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁸² www.rd-alliance.org/event/rda-knowledge-base-hands-on-feedback-session-1/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

¹⁸³ rda.dansdemo.nl/rda-annotator (accessed 2025.06.02)

the RDA Annotator is available for download in the above link, and a full version containing additional feature upgrades is expected by P25 in October 2025 at the latest. WP4 is currently working on promoting its uptake among RDA Users, and to work with select RDA WGs to identify use cases and gather feedback.

The RDA Graph, which contains the underlying data of the RDA-KB is currently being integrated with the RDA website via an API connection. Once completed (estimated for July 2025), the underlying data will be synced daily with that of the RDA website, ensuring that data in the RDA-KB is always up-to-date.

6. Conclusion and perspectives

Recent updates within the RDA community mainly concern domain-agnostic activities, while updates on domain-specific activities primarily focus on the EOSC ecosystem. This dynamic may reflect a divergence of approach between the two initiatives, but it could also result from differences in how domain-agnostic initiatives are characterised. For example, OSCARS does not include a cluster category for the Engineering and Technology domain, unlike RDA.

Additionally, two of the initiatives previously tracked by the Landscape Analysis Service, the WorldFAIR and FAIR-IMPACT projects are now complete. This highlights the difficulty of providing a sustainable Landscape Analysis Service due to the rapid changes in the EOSC ecosystem. There is a need for a service that tracks the history and the relation between the various initiatives. Moreover, a lot of development in this space is resourced by projects / 'soft money'. When that is in a given institution it can be maintained. When it is things that are used by communities across institutions then there is a need to maintain those outputs. This is an important role of organisations like RDA and CODATA.

Geographically speaking, the trend appears to be moving toward the regionalisation of efforts, with RDA national nodes merging into regional groups, and RSE combining the Australian and New Zealand groups into a single Australasian community.

See you in December 2025 for the next edition of the Landscape Analysis Service report to see how the Open Science ecosystem is evolving.

